

Test the Effectiveness of Creative Thinking Skills in Resolving Administrative Problems in an Innovative Style – From the Point of View of the Faculty Members and Administrators of Bisha University - KSA

Author Details: Dr. Mozamil Ali Mohammed Osman-

Assistance Professor of Business Administration - Bisha University -Saudi Arabia

Abstract : *This study aims to test the effectiveness of using some of skills of creative thinking (sensitivity of problems – flexibility – originality – fluency and maintaining Direction) in resolving administrative problems , it has been applied to the university of Bisha – Saudi Arabia , we have been using descriptive and analytical method and I was design a questionnaire to collect data for the study from teachers and administrative and it has been distributed (85) questionnaires and it was retrieved (75) questionnaires, it has been using amount of statistical methods in the study like arithmetical average , standard deviation , cronbach's alpha , coefficient analysis , Pearson's correlation coefficient and regression analysis . The study has been reached to that there is moral positive relationship between sensitivity of problems and resolving administrative problems , in addition to the presence moral positive relationship between flexibility and resolving administrative problems , in addition to the presence moral positive relationship between originality and resolving administrative problems, and the result of study showed that there moral positive relationship between intellectual fluency and solving administrative problems , the study also has been reached to that there is moral positive relationship between maintaining Direction and resolving administrative problems.*

Keywords : *Creative Thinking Skills , sensitivity of problems , Flexibility , Originality , Fluency , Maintaining Direction , Administrative Problems.*

Introduction : Creativity is any form of action that leads to results that are novel, useful, and predictable. It is seeing analogies where no one else sees them. It is a means of testing hidden assumptions and thereby opening oneself or one's organization to needed changes. Creativity and innovation are becoming extremely important to the success of all business organizations because we are facing major and rapid changes in the environment, Organizations must become more innovative, developing the ability to quickly plan and implement adaptations to change in their environments ,and most business organizations are moving in our time to look for effective ways to face strategic challenges which contain a lot of problems and obstacles , which are trying to overcome it to achieve quality and quantity Leaps , overpass the competitor,s expectations making these organizations need innovative intellectual processes , and analytical methods , logical , philosophy help organizations for surviving ,sustainable development and competitiveness, by launching creative ideas to solve administrative problems in a creative style .

Problem of the study:

This study has tried to answer the following questions:

- 1) What is the relationship between sensitivity of problems and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style?
- 2) What is the relationship between flexibility and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style?
- 3) What is the relationship between originality and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style?
- 4) What is the relationship between fluency and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style?
- 5) What is the relationship between maintaining direction resolving administrative problems in an innovative style?

Significance and objectives of the study :

This study aims to test the effectiveness of creative thinking skills in resolving administrative problems in an innovative style – from the point of view of the faculty members and administrators, and that is through :

- 1) Determining the relationship between sensitivity of problems and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style.

- 2) Determining the relationship between flexibility and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style .
- 3) Determining the relationship between originality and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style .
- 4) Determining the relationship between fluency and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style.
- 5) Determining the relationship between maintaining direction and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style.

The limits of the study :

- 1) **Theoretical limit** : The study based on five variables will be referred to in the model of the study.
- 2) **Time limit** : The study based on data which have been collected from community of study - 2017.
- 3) **The Spatial limit** : Bisha University - KSA

Model of the study :

The model examines the relationship between the creative thinking skills (*Independent Variable*) and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style (*dependent variable*) in order to achieve the objectives of the study.

Figure [1]: Model of the study

Definitions of study variables : The following theoretical definition for study variables :

- 1) **Creative Thinking Skills** : A way of looking at problems or situations from a fresh perspective that suggests unorthodox solutions , Creative thinking can be stimulated both by an unstructured process such as brainstorming, and by a structured process such as lateral thinking , (Biasness Dictionary , 2017) . Creative thinking means thinking about new things or thinking in new ways. It is “thinking outside the box.” Often, creativity in this sense involves what is called lateral thinking, or the ability to perceive patterns that are not obvious (Alison Doyle , 2017)
- 2) **Sensitivity of Problems** : The ability to tell when something is wrong or is likely to go wrong. It does not involve solving the problem, only recognizing there is a problem.(o* NET online,2017)
- 3) **Flexibility** : The person's ability to change his mental state by changing attitudes . (Al-samraey , 2000)
- 4) **Originality** : Originality is the aspect of created or invented works as being new or novel, and thus distinguishable from reproductions, clones, forgeries, or derivative works. An original work is one not received from others nor one copied from or based upon the work of others. It is a work created with a unique style and substance.(Macfarlane, (2007)

- 5) **Fluency** : Ability to produce the largest number of creative ideas . ((Al-samraey , 2000).
- 6) **Maintaining Direction** : The ability of the individual to think about the problem for a long period of time until access to new solutions. (Abd-alazez,2009)
- 7) **Administrative Problems** : There is a gap between the current situation and the desired situation. (Fathy,1999)

Figure [2]: Concept of the problems

The hypotheses of the study :

Depending on figure [1] the study is testing the following hypotheses :

H1: There is a positive relationship between sensitivity of problems and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style .

H2: There is a positive relationship between flexibility and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style.

H3: There is a positive relationship between originality and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style .

H4: There is a positive relationship between the fluency and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style .

H5: There is a positive relationship between the administrative problems and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style .

Methodology and Result :

Method, Measure, Sample and Data Collections :

To collect data from sample to test the hypotheses, a descriptive analysis method was used and a questionnaire designed to collect the data from the sample. The questionnaire formed in two categories, the first one to decide the characteristics of the sample like: education, work experience, age, gender... etc. The second group is to test the hypotheses of the study. The research paid a particular attention to sampling and data collection process. The decision makers in Bisha University - KSA have chosen to conduct this study. Before distributing all questioners, the formal or symbolic validity used to find the validity of data gathering. For this purpose a primary questionnaire was validated by some professors and experts. So that they comment of the questionnaire after this step the questionnaire was redesigned. The Cronbach's coefficient alpha test was conducted to measure the internal consistency reliability , the result will be shown in the table (1).

Table(1) :Reliability Test of Questionnaire Using Alpha Cronbakh

Variable	No of items	Alpha Cronbakh value
Sensitivity of Problems	6	85%
Flexibility	7	88%
Originality	6	86%
Fluency	6	85%
Maintaining Direction	7	87%
Resolving Administrative Problems in an Innovative Style	10	89%

As shown on table(1) all values of alpha Cronbakh are greater than 0.06 as result of this step, a proposed of the questionnaire was distributed (85 copies of the questionnaire) and only (90%) received and valid for analysis.

Measure Factor Analysis :

Factor analysis, is a useful tool for investigating, variable relationships , for complex concepts . It allows researchers, to investigate concepts ,that are not easily measured directly, by collapsing a large number of variables, into a few interpretable underlying factors, therefore the scales were submitted to principal component analysis using SPSS and the result of analysis for any variable of the study will be shown below:

Table (2): Rotated Component Matrix Of Sensitivity of Problems

Items	Component
SP1	0.887
SP2	0.831
SP3	0.872
SP4	0.865
SP5	0.889
SP6	0.887
Eigen Value	52.31
Eigen value Total	52.31
Kaiser –Meyer-Olkin (KMO)	0.656
Bartlett,s Test of Sphercity	358.431

From table (2) it is seen that the rotated matrix came in one component and the loading value for all items are greater than 0.5(cut point) in addition, eigen values greater than one and the result (SP1, SP2, SP3, SP4, SP5, SP6) , were chosen items to measure **Sensitivity of Problems** .

Table (3): Rotated Component Matrix Of Flexibility

Items	Component
FL1	0.886
FL2	0.850
FL3	0.870
FL4	0.820
FL5	0.788
FL6	0.880
FL7	0.840
Eigen Value	59.40
Eigen value Total	59.40
Kaiser –Meyer-Olkin (KMO)	0.680
Bartlett,s Test of Sphercity	375.20

From table (3) it is seen that the rotated matrix came in one component and the loading value for all items is greater than 0.5(cut point) in addition, eigen values greater than one and the result (FL1, FL2, FL3, FL4, FL5, FL6, FL7) were chosen items to measure **flexibility**.

Table (4): Rotated Component Matrix Of Originality

Items	Component
OR1	0.878
OR2	0.890
OR3	0.790
OR4	0.885
OR5	0.884
OR6	0.887
Eigen Value	52.14
Eigen value Total	52.14
Kaiser –Meyer-Olkin (KMO)	0.605
Bartlett,s Test of Sphercity	404.660

From table (4) it is seen that the rotated matrix came in one component and the loading value for all items are greater than 0.5(cut point) in addition, eigen values greater than one and the result (OR1, OR2, OR3, OR4, OR5, OR6) were chosen items to measure **originality** .

Table (5): Rotated Component Matrix Of Fluency

Items	Component
FLU1	0.878
FLU2	0.860
FLU3	0.795
FLU4	0.887
FLU5	0.889
FLU6	0.884
Eigen Value	51.93
Eigen value Total	51.93
Kaiser –Meyer-Olkin (KMO)	0.642
Bartlett,s Test of Sphercity	364.661

From table (5) it is seen that the rotated matrix came in one component and the loading value for all items are greater than 0.5(cut point) in addition, eigen values greater than one and the result (FLU1, FLU2, FLU3, FLU4, FLU5, FLU6) were chosen items to measure **fluency**.

Table (6): Rotated Component Matrix Of Maintaining Direction

Items	Component
MD1	0.881
MD2	0.850
MD3	0.875
MD4	0.865
MD5	0.888
MD6	0.792
MD7	0.884
Eigen Value	60.35
Eigen value Total	60.35
Kaiser –Meyer-Olkin (KMO)	0.655
Bartlett,s Test of Sphercity	350.425

Items	Component	
	1	2
QSP1	0.887	-0.330
QSP2	0.831	-0.479
QFL1	0.886	-0.089
QFL2	0.850	-0.241
QOR1	0.878	-0.096
QOR2	0.880	-0.320
QFLU1	0.878	0.586
QFLU2	0.860	0.625
QMD1	0.881	0.550
QMD2	0.850	0.4620
Eigen Values	86.91	35.97
Eigenvalue Total	122.88	
Kaiser –Meyer-Olkin (KMO)	0.663	
Bartlett,s Test of Sphercity	413.260	

From table (6) it is seen that the rotated matrix came in one component and the loading value for all items are greater than 0.5(cut point) in addition, eigen values greater than one and the result (MD1, MD2, MD3, MD4, MD5, MD6, MD7) were chosen items to measure **maintaining direction** .

Table (7): Rotated Component Matrix Of Resolving Administrative Problems in an Innovative Style

From the table (7) it is seen that the loading of items and the matrix came in two components and eigen values of any one of them is greater than 1.0 therefore, some items were deleted from the matrix if the item has a negative loading value or less than the cut point (0.5). Reliability measured for both components (reliability of component one=0.872, reliability of component two = 0.520) based on this result items of the first component (QSP1, QSP2, QFL1, QFL2, QOR1, QOR2) were used for measuring **resolving administrative problems in an innovative style** .

Table (8): Descriptive Analysis of The Study Variable

Variable	Type Of	Arithmetic	standard
Sensitivity of Problems	Independent	4.12	0.54
Flexibility	Independent	4.32	0.55
Originality	Independent	4.40	0.54
Fluency	Independent	4.44	0.54
Maintaining Direction	Independent		
Resolving Administrative Problems in an Innovative Style	Dependent	4.22	0.54

Note: All variables used a 5-point Likert scale (1= strongly disagree, 5= strongly agree)

Test of hypotheses of the study :

The aim of this linear regression analysis is to test the hypothesis of the study and to determine the strongly and the type of the relation. The result will be shown on the next table.

1)Relation between Sensitivity of Problems and Resolving Administrative Problems in an Innovative Style :

The aim of this linear regression analysis is to test the hypothesis (relation between **Sensitivity of Problems** and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style) and to determine the strongly and the type of the relation . The result will be shown on the next table.

Table (9): Relation between Sensitivity of Problems and Resolving Administrative Problems in an Innovative Style

Variable	Resolving Administrative Problems in an Innovative Style	
	Beta	Sig.
Sensitivity of Problems	**0.657	.000
R Square=.432 , Adjusted R Square=.423,F=40.710 and Sig=0.000		

The result of linear regression analysis between the dependent variable (sensitivity of problems) and independent variable (resolving administrative problems in an innovative style) it is seen on table (9) the result shows the model of research is statistically significant ($F=40.710$ and $**p<0.01$) and a positive significant relation between sensitivity of problems and the resolving administrative problems in an innovative style ($Beta=0.657$ and $Sig. = 0.000$) **founded**.

2)Relation between Flexibility and Resolving Administrative Problems in an Innovative Style :

The aim of this linear regression analysis is to test the hypothesis (relation between flexibility and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style) and to determine the strongly and the type of the relation . The result will be shown in the next table.

Table (10): Relation between Flexibility and Resolving Administrative Problems in an Innovative Style :

Variable	Resolving Administrative Problems in an Innovative Style	
	Beta	Sig.
Flexibility	**0.662	.000
R Square=.438 , Adjusted R Square=.429,F=45.330 and Sig=0.000		

The result of linear regression analysis between the dependent variable (flexibility) and independent variable (resolving administrative problems in an innovative style) it is seen in table (10) the result shows the model of research is statistically significant ($F=45.330$ and $**p<0.01$) and a positive significant relation between flexibility and resolving administrative Problems in an innovative style ($Beta=0.662$ and $Sig. = 0.000$) **founded**.

3)Relation between Originality and Resolving Administrative Problems in an Innovative Style:

The aim of this linear regression analysis is to test the hypothesis (relation between originality and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style) and to determine the strongly and the type of the relation . The result will be shown in the next table.

Table (11): Relation between originality and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style:

Variable	Resolving Administrative Problems in an Innovative Style	
	Beta	Sig.
Originality	**0.447	.000
R Square=.199 , Adjusted R Square=.188,F=37.250 and Sig=0.000		

The result of linear regression analysis between the dependent variable (originality) and independent variable (resolving administrative problems in an innovative style) it is seen in table (11) the result shows the model of research is statistically significant ($F=37.250$ and $**p<0.01$) and a positive significant relation between originality and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style ($Beta=0.447$ and $Sig. = 0.000$) **founded**.

4)Relation between fluency and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style :

The aim of this linear regression analysis is to test the hypothesis (relation between fluency and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style) and to determine the strongly and the type of the relation . The result will be shown in the next table.

Table (12): Relation between fluency and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style

Variable	Resolving Administrative Problems in an Innovative	
	Beta	Sig.
Fluency	**0.447	.000
R Square=.299 , Adjusted R Square=.204,F=43.210 and Sig=0.000		

The result of linear regression analysis between the dependent variable (fluency) and independent variable (resolving administrative problems in an innovative style) it is seen in table (12) the result shows the model of research is statistically significant ($F=43.210$ and $**p<0.01$) and a positive significant relation between fluency and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style ($Beta=0.447$ and $Sig. = 0.000$) **founded**.

5)Relation between maintaining direction and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style :

The aim of this linear regression analysis is to test the hypothesis (relation between maintaining direction and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style) and to determine the strongly and the type of the relation . The result will be shown in the next table.

Table (13): Relation between maintaining and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style

Variable	Resolving Administrative Problems in an Innovative	
	Beta	Sig.
Maintaining Direction	**0.657	.000
R Square=.432 , Adjusted R Square=.413,F=49. 516 and Sig=0.000		

The result of linear regression analysis between the dependent variable (maintaining direction) and independent variable (resolving administrative problems in an innovative style) it is seen on table (13) the result shows the model of research is statistically significant ($F=49.516$ and $**p<0.01$) and a positive significant relation between maintaining direction and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style ($Beta=0.657$ and $Sig. = 0.000$) **founded.**

Summary of hypothesis testing :

Item	Statement of Hypothesis	Remark
H1	There is a positive relationship between sensitivity of problems and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style	Fully Supported
H2	There is a positive relationship between flexibility and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style	Fully Supported
H3	There is a positive relationship between originality and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style	Fully Supported
H4	There is a positive relationship between fluency and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style	Fully Supported
H5	There is a positive relationship between maintaining direction and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style	Fully Supported

Note : Fully Supported means the relation is significant and positive.

Results :

The purpose of this research is to test the effectiveness of creative thinking skills in resolving administrative problems in an innovative style – from the point of view of the faculty members and administrators of Bisha University - KSA , based on that the study concluded that there is statistical significance relationship between :

- 1) Sensitivity of problems and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style.
- 2) Flexibility and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style .
- 3) Originality and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style.

- 4) Fluency and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style .
- 5) Maintaining direction and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style .

Findings :

Analyzing the questions revealed the following result :

The result of linear regression analysis between the dependent variable (sensitivity of problems) and independent variable (resolving administrative problems in an innovative style) it is seen on table (9) the result shows the model of research is statistically significant ($F=40.710$ and $**p<0.01$) and a positive significant relation between sensitivity of problems and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style , the result of linear regression analysis between the dependent variable (flexibility) and independent variable (resolving administrative problems in an innovative style) it is seen in table (10) the result shows the model of research is statistically significant ($F=45.330$ and $**p<0.01$) and a positive significant relation between flexibility and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style, on the other hand the result of linear regression analysis between the dependent variable (originality) and independent variable (resolving administrative problems in an innovative style) it is seen in table (11) the result shows the model of research is statistically significant ($F=37.250$ and $**p<0.01$) and a positive significant relation between originality and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style , and the result of linear regression analysis between the dependent variable (fluency) and independent variable (resolving administrative problems in an innovative style) it is seen in table (12) the result shows the model of research is statistically significant ($F=43.210$ and $**p<0.01$) and a positive significant relation between fluency and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style, also , the result of linear regression analysis between the dependent variable (maintaining direction) and independent variable (resolving administrative problems in an innovative style) it is seen in table (13) the result shows the model of research is statistically significant ($F=49.516$ and $**p<0.01$) and a positive significant relation between maintaining direction and resolving administrative problems in an innovative style .

Recommendations :

This study recommends the following :

1. The possibility of applying this study In other similar organizations.
2. Consolidating the concept of thought freedom when administrative problems occur .
3. Consolidate the principle of delegation of powers .
4. Urge of suggestions , and linking it to a system of incentives , in order to develop effective systems of creativity to encourages university staff to practice creative thinking .

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